

1 **Influence of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ composites on mechanical and photocatalytic performances for**
2 **cement pastes and recycled aggregates**

3 Yidong Xu^a, Bowen Lin^b, Xiaoniu Yu^{c*}, Shi-Tong Li^d

4 ^aSchool of Civil Engineering and Architecture, NingboTech University, Ningbo 315100, China

5 ^bSchool of Civil Engineering, Chongqing Jiaotong University, Chongqing 400074, China

6 ^cJiangsu Key Laboratory of Construction Materials, Southeast University, Nanjing 211189, China

7 ^dSchool of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore
8 639798, Singapore

9 *Corresponding author Email: xnyu09@163.com

10 **Abstract:** In order to study the effect of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ on the properties of cement
11 paste and recycled aggregates, based on the memory effect of Layered Double Hydroxides
12 (LDHs), the MgAl-LDO (MgAl-LDHs calcined products) TiO₂ were mixed during the
13 reconstruction of MgAl-LDHs laminates, and then MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ composites were
14 synthesized. The performance changes of cement paste were characterized by hydration
15 heat test, microscopic morphology of hydration products, physical properties and
16 mechanical properties of cement paste. The effect of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ on the
17 multi-interface transition zone (ITZ, interface between old paste and new paste) of
18 recycled aggregates was studied by the micro-morphology, meso-mechanical properties,
19 and element diffusion behavior. The photocatalytic activity of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ loaded
20 on recycled aggregates was evaluated by simulating the degradation of methylene blue
21 under the sunlight. The results showed that the addition of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ promoted
22 the initial hydration reaction of Ordinary Portland cement (OPC) and induced and

23 promoted the growth and formation of cement hydration crystal products. Initial setting
24 time and final setting time were shortened, and the compressive strength of hardened paste
25 was improved when MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ composites were added to cement paste. The
26 MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ could make the ITZ of recycled aggregates more compact and improve
27 structural properties of the ITZ. The MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ had a certain diffusion effect in the
28 ITZ. The total degradation efficiency of methylene blue reached 82.2% by the 5-10mm of
29 MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ loaded on recycle aggregates under the simulated sunlight for 80 min.

30 **Keywords:** MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂; interfacial transition zone; recycled aggregate;
31 photocatalytic activity; compressive strength

32 **1 Introduction**

33 Now, building materials, as an important basic raw material for the national economy, shoulder
34 the important mission of providing material support for the construction of ecological civilization.
35 The development and application of recycled concrete has largely solved the problem of
36 construction waste in urbanization construction and demolition of old and new projects, and the
37 resource utilization of construction waste has been realized to a certain extent [1]. However, with
38 the continuous development of highway and construction industries, recycled concrete has been
39 unable to meet the increasing technical requirements of various industries due to its low strength,
40 low toughness and weak interface transition zone (ITZ) [2-4]. The influence of nanomaterials on the
41 components of recycled concrete system has been studied, and the research focus is on the influence
42 of nanomaterials on the performance of cement-based materials [5] and recycled aggregates [6].

43 After a period of research, green and non-toxic nanomaterials represented by TiO₂ have entered

44 the field of view of scholars. It has been found that adding TiO_2 nanomaterials to traditional
45 cement-based materials can improve the basic properties of cementitious materials [7-10]. The
46 addition of TiO_2 can promote the early cement hydration [11], reduce the number of microcracks
47 [12], and has certain photocatalytic properties in the cement paste [13]. The application environment
48 of concrete can better exert the pollutant degradation function of TiO_2 . The nano- TiO_2 is filled into
49 internal voids of recycled aggregates to achieve high photocatalytic efficiency [14]. In the
50 photocatalytic expanded shale (PES) preparing photocatalytic exposed aggregate concrete (PEAC),
51 the PEAC can provide more TiO_2 active sites [15]. However, scholars have found that TiO_2 itself
52 has certain defects with the deepening of research [16-19]. The 28-day compressive strength of
53 photocatalytic cement composites with 10% TiO_2 can be reduced by 12% due to the agglomeration
54 of nano- TiO_2 particles in the cement paste [20]. The low photodegradation efficiency, easy
55 agglomeration and deactivation of TiO_2 limit its application in concrete systems. Therefore, many
56 pioneering works are still needed to develop potential nanomaterials that can improve concrete
57 performances.

58 Layered Double Hydroxides (LDHs) have received extensive attention in the past decades due
59 to their multifunctional properties [21-24]. LDHs are layered crystalline materials belonging to the
60 family of anionic clays with hexagonal or octahedral crystal structures [25]. LDHs and their
61 calcination products (LDO) are porous materials with large specific surface area, strong adsorption
62 [26], and anion exchange capacity [27]. At the same time, when the calcination product LDO of
63 LDHs at a certain temperature is mixed with an aqueous solution, its structure can be partially
64 restored to LDHs with an ordered layered structure. This memory effect makes LDHs have unique

65 structural tunable properties [28]. Based on the excellent properties of LDHs, some scholars have
66 carried out material composite research on LDHs, and it has been confirmed that LDHs are suitable
67 as carriers of nanoparticles [29-31], which can use to improve the performance of concrete.

68 In view of the above problems, based on the memory effect of LDHs, MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂
69 composites are synthesized by mixing MgAl-LDO with TiO₂ during the reconstruction of
70 MgAl-LDHs laminates. The microscopic characterization of the prepared composites is carried out.
71 At the same time, MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ composites are mixed with cement paste and recycled
72 aggregates. The effect of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ on the performance of cement paste is studied through
73 hydration heat test, micromorphology of hydration products, physical properties and mechanical
74 properties of cement paste. The effect of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ on the regenerated aggregate ITZ2 (the
75 interface of the old slurry and the new slurry) is studied and characterized by the micro-morphology,
76 meso-mechanical properties, element diffusion behavior. The photocatalytic activity of recycled
77 aggregates loaded MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ is evaluated by simulating the degradation of methylene blue
78 under the sunlight.

79 **2 Materials and methods**

80 *2.1. Materials*

81 Magnesium aluminum hydroxide carbonate ($Mg_6Al_2(CO_3)(OH)_{16} \cdot 4H_2O$, MgAl-LDHs, AR)
82 powder was purchased from Guangdong Wengjiang Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd, China. The P25
83 (commercial TiO₂) and methylene blue were commercially available. Ordinary Portland Cement
84 (P.O 42.5), produced by Lanxi Zhuge South Cement Co., Ltd, China. The basic performance
85 indicators of recycled coarse aggregates were shown in Table 1, which met the technical

86 requirements in the specification "Recycled coarse aggregate for concrete" (GB/T 25177-2010).

87 Table 1 Basic performance indicators of recycled coarse aggregates.

Particles size/mm	Apparent density/kg·m ⁻³	Water absorption/%	Crushing index/%	Micro-powder content/%
5-20	2510	7.0	17.9	1.8

88 2.2. Samples preparation

89 2.2.1 Preparation of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂

90 A certain amount of MgAl-LDHs powder was placed in a covered crucible, calcined in a
91 muffle furnace for 3 h (the heating rate was 8 °C/min, and the calcination temperature was 400 °C),
92 and then cooled to room temperature naturally. The obtained metal oxide was recorded as
93 MgAl-LDO.

94 Under magnetic stirring, a certain mass of TiO₂ and MgAl-LDO were mixed in 100 mL of
95 deionized water for 6 h. The obtained mixed solution was centrifuged, washed, and vacuum-dried at
96 50 °C for 12 h. Finally, the off-white MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ powder was obtained.

97 2.2.2. Preparation of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂-recycled aggregate

98 The MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ composites were loaded into the pores on the surface of the recycled
99 aggregate (RA). The specific loading process was as follows: crushing and sieving the concrete to
100 obtain a recycled aggregate with a particle size of 10-15 mm, washing their surface of the aggregate.
101 After cleaning the dust and soil, they were put in a 105 °C of oven for 24 hours. After cooling,
102 recycled aggregates were immersed in the 0.6% of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ solution for 24 hours, and
103 then placed it in an oven at 105 °C for 12 hours. The aggregates were cooled to room temperature to
104 obtain MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂-loaded recycled aggregates, denoted as MTRA. The loading process of the
105 TiO₂-loaded recycled aggregates was the same as that of MTRA, and the TiO₂-loaded recycled

106 aggregates was recorded as TRA.

107 2.2.3. Preparation of samples for interfacial study of recycled aggregates

108 Recycled aggregates (RA, TRA, MTRA) were vertically added into a 40 mm × 40 mm × 40
109 mm of mold, and the cement paste was prepared at a water-cement ratio of 0.5 and demolded after
110 curing at room temperature for 24 hours. The prepared slices (40mm×40mm×5mm) were polished
111 and tested with 320-mesh, 800-mesh, and 1200-mesh sandpaper in the increasing order of particles
112 size. The microhardness test of the interfacial transition zone (ITZ) was carried out with the
113 obtained samples. At the same time, some samples were selected for SEM test. Since the surface of
114 the recycled aggregate mainly plays the role of adsorption was the old porous paste on the surface
115 [32], so the MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ supporting layer was almost concentrated in the old paste part. The
116 research objects in the interface study were the ITZ2 interface of old paste and new paste.

117 3.3. Characterization of specimens

118 The S-4800 Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy of Hitachi Corporation of Japan
119 was used to observe the micromorphology of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂, hydration products of cement paste,
120 and ITZ of recycled concrete, the acceleration voltage was 5KV, and the magnification was
121 20~800000 times. In the energy dispersive X-ray spectrometer, the element surface distribution
122 analysis for the ITZ of recycled concrete was carried out.

123 The X-ray powder diffractometer (XRD, CuK α , $\lambda=0.15406\text{nm}$, D8 ADVANCE, Bruker) was
124 used to determine hydration products of cement paste [33, 34]. The acceleration voltage was 40KV,
125 the maximum output current was 40mA. The scanning range was 10°-70°, and the maximum
126 scanning speed was 5°/min.

127 The Vickers hardness value test was carried out on the ITZ2 in the HV-1000 microhardness
128 tester. The schematic diagram of the point group of the microhardness was shown in Figure 1.

129

130 Figure 1 Schematic diagram of the point group of the microhardness.

131 The TAM Air Isothermal Calorimeter 8-channel isothermal calorimeter was used to test the
132 hydration heat of cement paste loaded with MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂, and its water-cement ratio was 0.5.

133 The tests of water requirement, setting time and soundness for standard consistency of cement
134 paste were carried out in accordance with the provisions of "Testing methods for water requirement
135 of normal consistency, setting time and soundness of the portland cement " (GB/T1346-2001).

136 A cement block with a size of 40mm×40mm×40mm was prepared at a water-cement ratio of
137 0.5. Three samples were in each group. After the blocks were cured to the age, they were taken out
138 for compressive strength testing.

139 **3 Results and discussion**

140 *3.1. Microstructure of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ composites*

141 The microstructures of TiO₂ and MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ composites were observed by SEM images,
142 as shown in Figure 2. The average size of TiO₂ was approximately 20-30 nm. The micro-particles
143 (0.5-2 μm) were formed by the spherical agglomeration, and the agglomeration phenomenon was
144 obvious (Figure 2a). The morphology of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ composites showed that TiO₂
145 nanoparticles were dispersed on the surface of the LDHs lamellae and in the inter-connected

146 plate-like gaps, and the agglomeration phenomenon was greatly improved, as shown in Figure 2b.
147 The result indicated that TiO_2 nanoparticles could be largely exposed on the surface of LDHs
148 particles after hydration with calcined LDHs based on the memory effect of LDHs. The dispersion
149 degree of TiO_2 was greatly improved.

150
151 (a) TiO_2

(b) MgAl-LDHs/ TiO_2

152 Figure 2 Microstructure of materials.

153 3.2. Influence of MgAl-LDHs/ TiO_2 composites on cement paste

154 3.2.1 The effect of MgAl-LDHs/ TiO_2 composites on the hydration heat of cement paste

155 The rate of hydration heat release and total amount of heat released of cement paste with 1%,
156 2%, 3%, 4% of MgAl-LDHs/ TiO_2 and the control group were measured, and the results are shown
157 in Figure 3. It can be seen from Figure 3a that the curve of hydration heat release of different
158 dosages of MgAl-LDHs/ TiO_2 was basically the same as that of pure cement, indicating that the
159 MgAl-LDHs/ TiO_2 does not change the hydration process. In the initial stage, there were certain
160 differences in the rate of the hydration heat release when different dosages of MgAl-LDHs/ TiO_2
161 were mixed into the cement, and the peak of the hydration heat release was between 0.08-0.11W/g
162 at 0-0.1h. With the increase of the content of MgAl-LDHs/ TiO_2 composites, the peak of the reaction
163 during the initial period decreased continuously until it was stabilized.

164 The peak of the hydration heat release in the acceleration period was basically between
165 0.004-0.006W/g, as shown in Figure 3c. The peak of the hydration heat release in the acceleration
166 period continued to increase with the increase of the MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ content (1% to 4%) until it
167 was approximately equal. The hydration heat release of the 4% MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ content was
168 about 25%, which was higher than that of pure cement. The peak value of the cement acceleration
169 period is about 2h earlier. The stage of the hydration heat release was concentrated in 0-0.1h and
170 4-12h, corresponded to the two hydration stages of the initial stage and the acceleration stage,
171 respectively (Figure 3c). The hydration heat release of the cement mixed with MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂
172 composites at all ages was higher than that of control group. With the increase of the content of
173 MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂, the total amount of the hydration heat release increased. When 1% content was
174 increased to 3%, the increase in total hydration heat release remained at 5-10%. When the dosage
175 was increased from 3% to 4%, the total amount for 3d of hydration heat release was almost
176 unchanged.

177
178 (a) 3d rate of hydration heat release

(b) 1h rate of hydration heat release

(c) The rate of hydration heat release during acceleration period (d) The total amount of heat release in 3 days

Figure 3 Curves of hydration heat release and total heat release of cement paste loaded with MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ composites.

Above results showed that the addition of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ composites could promote the initial hydration reaction of the cement at 0-3d, which reduced the rate of the hydration heat release in the initial period of cement hydration, advanced the acceleration period, increased the rate of the hydration heat release in the acceleration period, and increased the amount of the hydration heat release. (1) This phenomenon could be attributed to the LDHs in the MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ had a certain interlayer anion exchange effect, which could adsorb SO₄²⁻ produced by the dissolution of cement clinker minerals and inhibited the formation of ettringite, thereby reducing the cracking of later hydration products caused by the swelling of ettringite. (2) The nucleation effect of nanomaterials could provide a nucleation point for the hydration of cement clinker minerals, and promoted the cement hydration to produce more C-S-H. The growth of C-S-H could accelerate the hydration of cement and improved the hydration rate of cement. (3) The large specific surface area of the MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ could absorb water molecules for the hydration reaction, increased the contact area during the hydration, and increased the collision probability of water molecules with

196 crystal nucleation sites, thereby accelerating the growth of C-S-H.

197 3.2.2. Influence of the MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ on hydration products of cement paste

198 In order to analyze the influence of the MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ on the hydration process of cement
199 paste and the composition of hydration products, under the water-cement ratio of 0.5, the content of
200 the MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ was selected as 0 and 3%, respectively, on the 3d and 28d age. The optimum
201 dosage of 3% MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ was based on the hydration heat test of the cement paste as the
202 standard. The test results were shown in Figure 4. It can be seen from the Figure 4 that diffraction
203 peaks of four groups of samples mainly corresponded to the hydration products of ettringite (AFt)
204 and calcium hydroxide (CH), as well as unhydrated tricalcium silicate (C₃S) and dicalcium silicate
205 (C₂S). No obvious new diffraction peaks appeared in XRD patterns of cement pastes hydrated for 3
206 d and 28 d with 3% of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂, which indicated that the addition of the
207 MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ did not change the types of cement hydration products. With the extension of
208 hydration age, the diffraction peak intensities of C₃S and C₂S in each group of samples were
209 weakened, while the diffraction peak intensities of CH and AFt were enhanced. However, at the
210 same age, whether it was 3d or 28d, by comparing the diffraction peaks of the samples, it can be
211 found that the CH and AFt diffraction peak intensities in cement samples mixed with 3%
212 MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ were significantly higher than those of the control. Diffraction peak intensities of
213 C₃S and C₂S were the opposite. This may be because the nucleation effect of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂
214 nanoparticles promoted the crystallization of the hydration product CH.

215

Figure 4 XRD patterns of 3d and 28d cement pastes.

216

217

218 Under the water-cement ratio of 0.5, the control sample and the 28d hardened sample of 3%

219 MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ cement paste were selected for SEM observation, and the influence of the

220 MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ on the interior of the hardened paste was analyzed, as shown in Figure 5. Figure

221 5 indicated that cement stones hardened for 28 days were mainly composed of fibrous C-S-H gel,

222 which was very obvious. It can be seen that fibrous C-S-H interweaves with each other, but it has a

223 certain weak area, and its structure is relatively less dense with more pores, as shown Figure 5a.

224 When the content of the MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ was 3%, the relatively stable microstructure was formed,

225 C-S-H crystals were interlaced growth, and the surface structure of hardened pastes was dense and

226 less pores compared with the control group (Figure 5b). Above results showed that the

227 MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ had a certain filling effect on cement.

230 Figure 5 SEM images of hardened cement pastes for 28 days.

231 *3.2.3. Influence of the MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ on the physical properties of cement paste*

232 In Table 2 and Figure 6a, it could be concluded that adding MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ composites to
233 cement would increase the water requirement for standard consistency of cement paste. The
234 standard consistency of cement paste increased with the increase of the MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ content.
235 The water requirement was also increasing, but the maximum was only 1.6%. This was related with
236 the microstructure and specific surface area of the MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂. The specific surface area of
237 the MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ was much larger than that of cement, and it had strong adsorption effect to
238 water molecules, resulting in an increase in the water requirement of standard consistency for
239 cement.

240 The initial setting time of cement in the control group was 172 min and the final setting time
241 was 310 min, as shown Figure 6b. The addition of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ composites would affect the
242 setting time of cement, and with the increase of its content, the initial setting and final setting time
243 began to decrease. When the content of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ was 3%, the initial setting time of the
244 cement sample was 12 minutes, which was lower than that of the control group. The final setting
245 time was 30 minutes that was also lower than that of the control group. Above results indicated that
246 the MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ could shorten the setting time of cement. The setting time decreased with the

247 increase of the content of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂. Because the huge surface area of the
 248 MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ was easy to become the nucleation point of C-S-H gel, promoting its formation,
 249 thereby accelerating the hardening of cement paste.

250 Table 2 Influence of the MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ on water requirement, setting time and soundness for
 251 cement of standard consistency.

Samples No.	Standard consistency water requirement /%	Initial setting time /min	Final setting time /min	Soundness
Control	28.2	172	310	Qualification
1%	29.0	168	300	Qualification
2%	29.4	162	287	Qualification
3%	30.0	160	280	Qualification

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253

254

255 Figure 6 Effect of the MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ on the physical properties of cement paste.

256 *3.2.4. Effect of the MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ on the mechanical properties of cement paste*

257 Figure 7 showed the effect of different dosages of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ on the compressive
 258 strength of cement paste at each age. Compared with the control group, the compressive strength of
 259 3d, 7d and 28d groups obviously increased with the increase of the MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂. The addition
 260 of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ could significantly improve the compressive strength of cement blocks, and it
 261 increased with the increase of the content of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂. When the content of

262 MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ was 3%, the compressive strength of cement blocks was maximum. Compared
263 with the control group, the compressive strength of cement blocks at 3d, 7d and 28d had increased
264 by 53.77%, 33.45% and 25.69%, respectively. Among them, the 3d compressive strength of the
265 cement block with 3% of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ composites was close to the 7d compressive strength of
266 the control group. When the content of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ was 1% and 2%, the compressive strength
267 of the cement block at 28d increased by 5.88% and 24.26%, respectively. The schematic diagram of
268 the hydration mechanism was shown in Figure 8. When the content of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ increased,
269 the contact area of cement clinker increased, and MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ composites could provide a
270 large number of C-S-H nucleation sites, and a large number of cement particles and water molecules
271 were attached to the cement clinker. The surface of the composite material promoted the hydration
272 of cement, resulting in an increase in the strength of the system at various ages, especially in the
273 early strength improvement. The schematic diagram of the mechanism is shown in Figure 8.

274
275 Figure 7 Effect of the addition of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ on the compressive strength of cement
276 paste at different ages.

277

278

Figure 8 The schematic diagram of the hydration mechanism for cement.

279

3.3. Photocatalytic performance of recycle aggregates loaded with MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ composites

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3.3.1. Influence of photocatalytic materials

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Preparation parameters of photocatalytic recycle aggregates were shown in Table 3. The

282

methylene blue was regarded as the target pollutant, the photocatalytic degradation efficiency of

283

different photocatalytic aggregates under the simulated sunlight was investigated. The experimental

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results were shown in Figure 9. Figure 9 showed that the natural aggregate (NA) and TiO₂-natural

285

aggregate (TNA) had almost no adsorption capacity in the dark adsorption stage. The adsorption

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rate of the regenerated aggregate (RA) was similar to that of TiO₂ regenerated aggregate (TRA), its

287

value was about 5%. The adsorption efficiency of RA and TRA mainly contributed to the adsorption

288

of methylene blue on the porous surface of the recycled aggregate. The adsorption efficiency of

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MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂-natural aggregate (MTNA) was 8%. The MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ composites played a

290

main role of adsorption. The adsorption efficiency of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂-regenerated aggregate

291

(MTRA) was the highest, and its value was 22%. The reason for the high adsorption efficiency

292

might be the large amount of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ loaded on the surface of MTRA combined with the

293 porous surface of RA. The order of the adsorption efficiency from small to large in the dark
 294 adsorption stage was as follows: MTRA>MTNA>RA>TRA>TNA>NA.

295 Table 3 Preparation parameters of photocatalytic aggregates.

Samples No.	Photocatalytic materials	Aggregate types	Diameter/mm
RA	/	RA	5-10
TRA	TiO ₂	RA	5-10
MTRA	MgAl-LDHs/TiO ₂	NA	5-10
NA	/	NA	5-10
TNA	TiO ₂	NA	5-10
MTNA	MgAl-LDHs/TiO ₂	NA	5-10

296
 297 Figure 9 Degradation curves of the methylene blue by different photocatalytic aggregates.

298 In the photodegradation stage, it can be seen from the Blank curve that methylene blue had a
 299 certain self-degradation behavior under sunlight, and the NA and RA curves were parallel to the
 300 Blank curve, indicating that the NA and RA did not have the ability to degrade methylene blue
 301 under sunlight. The order of 80min photodegradation efficiency from large to small is: MTRA
 302 (60.2%)>MTNA (41%)>TRA (35.7%)>TNA (26%). The photodegradation efficiency of
 303 MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ as the surface loading layer was higher than that of the aggregate whose surface
 304 loading layer was TiO₂. The TNA showed the weakest photodegradation efficiency. The
 305 photodegradation efficiency of MTNA was slightly higher than that of TRA, which might be due to

306 the superior photodegradation ability of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ composites, even though natural
307 aggregates had weaker loading capacity for photocatalytic materials than recycled aggregates. The
308 loading capacity of natural aggregates was weak, but the superior photodegradation capacity of
309 MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ could offset some of the effects. The photocatalytic material was easily detached
310 from the surface of the natural aggregate due to the weak surface binding force. The MTRA showed
311 the best photodegradation rate of 60.2%, and the total degradation efficiency of MTRA reached
312 82.2% by combining the adsorption efficiency in the dark adsorption stage. The reasons for the high
313 degradation efficiency of the MTRA could be summarized as follows: (1) the MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂
314 was well loaded on recycled aggregates. (2) The adsorption and photocatalysis effects of the
315 MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ were performed simultaneously. (3) Recycled aggregates themselves had
316 adsorption capacity.

317 *3.3.2. The effect of recycled aggregate particles size*

318 Three kinds of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂-recycle aggregates with different particle sizes of 5-10mm,
319 10-15mm, and 15-20mm were prepared experimentally to study the effect of different particle sizes
320 of aggregates on their degradation efficiency. The test results were shown in Figure 10. In the dark
321 adsorption stage, the adsorption efficiency of the RA control group of 5-10mm was 5%, as shown in
322 Figure 10. The adsorption efficiency of the MTRA at 5-10mm was the highest, reaching 22%. The
323 adsorption efficiency of the MTRA of 10-15mm and 15-20mm was 17% and 15%, respectively. The
324 adsorption efficiency of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂-recycle aggregates tended to decrease with the increase
325 of aggregate particles size.

326 The MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂-recycle aggregates also showed a similar trend in the dark adsorption

327 stage during the photodegradation stage. The photodegradation efficiency of MTRA was the highest,
 328 reaching 60.2%. The photodegradation efficiency of MTRA of 10-15mm was 55%. The
 329 photodegradation efficiency of MTRA of 15-20mm was 51%. The order of photodegradation
 330 efficiency was: 5-10mm MTRA>10-15mm MTRA>15-20mm MTRA. The reason for this trend of
 331 adsorption efficiency and photodegradation efficiency might be that the smaller the particle size of
 332 aggregates under the same mass, the more nano-pores on its surface, the stronger the adsorption
 333 capacity, and the more MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ loaded on the surface of the recycled aggregate, resulting
 334 in the trend of its degradation efficiency.

335
 336 Figure 10 Degradation curve of methylene blue with different aggregate particles size.

337 *3.4. The influence of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ on the ITZ2 of recycled concrete*

338 *3.4.1. Microstructure of ITZ2*

339 The research objects in this section were the ITZ2 interface between the old paste and the new
 340 paste. SEM images of recycled concrete were used to test and analyze the micro-morphology at the
 341 interface of ITZ2 at a water-cement ratio of 0.5, as shown in Figure 11. There were obvious cracks
 342 in the ITZ2 interface between ordinary recycled aggregate and new paste, and the interface structure

343 was relatively loose and had many pores. However, the structures of MTRA-ITZ2 (TiO₂-recycled
344 aggregates) and TRA-ITZ2 (MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂-recycle aggregates) were relatively compact, and the
345 interface micro-crack voids were smaller. The compactness of the MTRA-ITZ2 interface was
346 increased due to the existence of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ composites, and the interface properties were
347 improved. The order of interface compactness was: MTRA-ITZ2>TRA-ITZ2>RA-ITZ2.

350 Figure 11 Micromorphology of ITZ2 interface between the loaded recycled aggregate and the paste
351 at a water-cement ratio of 0.5.

352 3.4.2. Meso-mechanical properties of ITZ2

353 The microhardness test was carried out on the interface between the old mortar of recycled
354 coarse aggregate and the pure paste (ITZ2) of different photocatalytic materials loading layers under
355 the water-cement ratio of 0.5. The measured test results were shown in Table 4 and Figure 12. The
356 abscissa from left to right was from the old paste to the new paste of recycle aggregates. The
357 interface between the old paste and the new paste (ITZ2) was essentially the same material, the
358 interface transition area between the two was not obvious [35]. The surface of the old paste had a
359 large number of pores, which could absorb cement particles of the new paste. It also accommodated
360 the growth of hydration products, so that an embedded structure was formed between the old paste
361 and the new paste. Therefore, the compactness of the ITZ2 was similar to that of the old and new

362 pastes [36, 37]. Under the same water-cement ratio, there were certain differences in the interfacial
363 transition zone of the recycled aggregate between the three different loaded layers, indicating that
364 the nano-photocatalytic material loading layer on the surface of the recycled aggregate had a certain
365 influence on the structural properties of the ITZ2. At a water-cement ratio of 0.5, the thickness of
366 the interfacial transition zone of the MTRA group was the smallest and the average value of its
367 microhardness was slightly higher than that of the TRA and RA groups, indicating that the
368 MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ and TiO₂ loaded on recycled aggregates were beneficial to the improvement of
369 recycled concrete. The improvement effect of the MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ loaded layer was better than
370 that of TiO₂. This could be attributed to the nucleation effect of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ nanoparticles,
371 which could provide nucleation sites for the hydration of cement clinker minerals at the interface,
372 which could also promote the hydration of cement to produce more C-S-H and promoted the growth
373 of C-S-H. The crystallization of hydration products was accelerated at the interface. The large
374 specific surface area of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ composites could absorb water molecules for the
375 hydration reaction, increased the contact area of the cement hydration at the interface. The collision
376 probability between crystal nucleation site and water molecule was increased, thereby accelerating
377 the growth of C-S-H at the interface.

378

Table 4 ITZ2 parameters.

Specimens No.	RA	TRA	MTRA
ITZ2 Microhardness value/MPa	99.2	108.8	115.6
ITZ2 Width/ μm	53.2	47.5	43.2

379

380

381

Figure 12 Effect of different photocatalytic recycled aggregate loading layers on the

382

microhardness of concrete ITZ2 interface.

383

3.4.3. Diffusion behavior of chemical elements in the ITZ2

384

The diffusion behavior of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ composites loaded on the surface of recycled

385

aggregates in concrete systems was observed to verify the feasibility of the application of

386

photocatalytic recycled aggregates. The diffusion behavior of chemical elements of

387

MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ composites was investigated by EDS images. The surface distribution of the Ti

388

element was calibrated in the ITZ2 interface, as shown in Figures 13 and 14. In Figures 13a and 14a,

389

the white area on the left was the new paste, and the gray area on the right was the old paste. It can

390

be seen from the figure that no matter whether the surface loaded layer of recycled aggregates was

391

the TiO₂ or MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂, the Ti element not only existed on the surface of the old paste, but

392

also diffused through the interface transition zone into the new paste. The diffusion effect of

393

MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ composites in the new paste was better than that of TiO₂. The result showed that

394

the loading process was to fix the photocatalytic materials on the surface of recycle aggregates. The

395

photocatalytic material participated in the entire hydration process of cement, and it had a certain

396 diffusion effect, which made the photocatalytic reaction occurred on the surface of recycled
397 aggregate and concrete. The result proved the feasibility of the application for photocatalytic
398 materials loaded on recycled aggregates.

399
400 (a) Original morphology (b) surface distribution of Ti elements (c) Superimposed topography of elements

401 Figure 13 Distribution of Ti elements at the TRA-ITZ2 interface.

402
403 (a) Original morphology (b) Surface distribution of Ti elements (c) Superimposed topography of elements

404 Figure 14 Distribution of Ti elements at the MTRA-ITZ2 interface.

405 3 Conclusions

406 (1) On the basis of optimizing the preparation conditions of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ photocatalytic
407 materials, the MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ was mixed into cement paste to explore the effect of
408 MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ on the performance of cement paste. The research results showed that the
409 MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ had a positive effect on cement paste. The addition of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂
410 promotes the initial hydration reaction of OPC, which could induce and promote the growth and
411 formation of cement hydration crystal products.

412 (2) The microscopic morphology of the cement was made more compact. The addition of
413 MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ shortened the initial setting time and final setting time of the cement paste, and
414 improved the compressive strength of cement blocks.

415 (3) The effect of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ loaded on recycled aggregates on the ITZ and the
416 adsorption photocatalytic performance were studied. The results showed that MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂
417 composites could make the ITZ2 structure more compact, which improved the interface properties.
418 The photocatalytic materials had a certain diffusion effect in the system, so that the photocatalytic
419 reaction could not only occur on the surface of the recycled aggregate, but also in the concrete paste.

420 (4) The optimal aggregate particles parameter of MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ was between 5 and 10mm.
421 The adsorption efficiency of methylene blue on the 5-10mm of recycled aggregates loaded
422 MgAl-LDHs/TiO₂ could reach 22% in 20 minutes, and the photodegradation efficiency of
423 methylene blue reached 60.2% after 80 minutes of simulated sunlight irradiation. The total
424 adsorption photocatalytic degradation efficiency reached 82.2% in the whole process.

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431 **References**

432 [1] X.N. Yu, L.Z. Sun, Strength, microstructure, and thermal conductivity of the insulation

- 433 wallboards prepared with rice husk fiber and recycled concrete aggregates. PLoS ONE
434 13(2018) e0203527.
- 435 [2] Z.G. Guo, J. Zhang, T. Jiang, T.X. Jiang, C. Chen, R. Bo, R Y. Sun, Development of sustainable
436 self-compacting concrete using recycled concrete aggregate and fly ash, slag, silica fume, Eur.
437 J. Environ. Civ. Eng. 26(2020) 1453-74.
- 438 [3] M. Sabău, J. Remolina Duran, Prediction of compressive strength of general-use concrete
439 mixes with recycled concrete aggregate, Int. J. Pavement Res. Technol. 15(2022) 73-85.
- 440 [4] J. Ahmad, R. Martinez-Garcia, J. de-Prado-Gil, K. Irshad, M.A. El-Shorbagy, R. Fediuk, N.I.
441 Vatin, Concrete with partial substitution of waste glass and recycled concrete aggregate,
442 Materials 15(2022) 430.
- 443 [5] F.P. Peng, Y.R. Ni, Q. Zhou, J.H. Kou, C.H. Lu, Z.Z. Xu, New g-C₃N₄ based photocatalytic
444 cement with enhanced visible-light photocatalytic activity by constructing muscovite
445 sheet/SnO₂ structures, Constr. Build. Mater. 179(2018) 315-325.
- 446 [6] H.R. Zhang, Y.X. Zhao, T. Meng, S.P. Shah, Surface treatment on recycled coarse aggregates
447 with nanomaterials, J. Mater. Civil Eng. 28(2016) 04015094.
- 448 [7] G. Liao, W. Yao, J.Q. Zuo, Preparation and characterization of zeolite/TiO₂ cement-based
449 composites with excellent photocatalytic performance, Materials 11(2018) 2485.
- 450 [8] J. Chen, S.C. Kou, C.S. Poon, Hydration and properties of nano-TiO₂ blended cement
451 composites, Cement Concrete Comp. 34(2012) 642-649.
- 452 [9] M.Z. Guo, T.C. Ling, C.S. Poon, Highly-efficient green photocatalytic cementitious materials
453 with robust weathering resistance: From laboratory to application, Environ. Pollut. 32(2021)

- 454 273.
- 455 [10] P.Q. Zhao, H. Wang, S.D. Wang, P. Du, L.C. Lu, X. Cheng, Assessment of nano-TiO₂
456 enhanced performance for photocatalytic polymer-sulphoaluminate cement composite coating,
457 J. Inorg. Organomet. P. 28(2018) 2439-2446.
- 458 [11] B.Y. Lee, K.E. Kurtis, Durability of photocatalytic cement subjected to nitrogen dioxide and
459 wet-dry cycling, Adv. Cem. Res. 32(2020) 139-147.
- 460 [12] D.C. Feng, N. Xie, C.W. Gong, Z. Leng, H.G. Xiao, H. Li, X.M. Shi, Portland cement paste
461 modified by TiO₂ nanoparticles: A microstructure perspective, Ind. Eng. Chem. Res. 52(2013)
462 11575-11582.
- 463 [13] E. Cerro-Prada, S. García-Salgado, M. Ángeles Quijano, F. Varela, Controlled synthesis and
464 microstructural properties of sol-gel TiO₂ nanoparticles for photocatalytic cement composites,
465 Nanomaterials 9(2019) 26.
- 466 [14] Y.D. Xu, R.Y. Jin, L. Hu, B. Li, W. Chen, J.S. Shen, P. Wu, J.K. Fang, Studying the mix design
467 and investigating the photocatalytic performance of pervious concrete containing TiO₂-soaked
468 recycled aggregates, J. Clean. Prod. 248(2020) 119281.
- 469 [15] F.Z. Wang, L. Yang, H. Wang, H.G. Yu, Facile preparation of photocatalytic exposed aggregate
470 concrete with highly efficient and stable catalytic performance, Chem. Eng. J. 264(2015)
471 577-586.
- 472 [16] D. Komaraiah, E. Radha, R.M.V. Ramana, J. Sivakumar, R. Sayanna, Effect of metal ions
473 doping on structural, optical properties and photocatalytic activity of anatase TiO₂ thin films,
474 Surf. Interface Anal. 53(2021) 194-205.

- 475 [17] Y. Nam, J.H. Lim, K.C. Ko, J.Y. Lee, Photocatalytic activity of TiO₂ nanoparticles: a
476 theoretical aspect, *J. Mater. Chem. A* 7(2019) 13833
- 477 [18] M. Wei, Z. Li, P. Chen, L. Sun, S. Kang, T. Dou, Y. Qu, L. Jing, N-rich doped anatase TiO₂
478 with smart defect engineering as efficient photocatalysts for acetaldehyde degradation,
479 *Nanomaterials* 12(2022) 1564.
- 480 [19] Q.Y. Li, J.W. Zhang, Z.S. Jin, C.X. Feng, J.W. Zhang, Z.S. Wu, Z.J.; Zhang, A novel TiO₂ with
481 a large amount of bulk intrinsic defects-Visible-light-responded photocatalytic activity induced
482 by foreign trap, *Chin. Sci. Bull.* 58(2013) 1675-1681.
- 483 [20] S.L. Feng, J.W. Song, F.H. Liu, X. Fu, H. Guo, J.L. Zhu, Q.L. Zeng, X.Y. Peng, X.F. Wang, Y.
484 Ouyang, F. Li, Photocatalytic properties, mechanical strength and durability of TiO₂/cement
485 composites prepared by a spraying method for removal of organic pollutants, *Chemosphere*
486 254(2020) 126813.
- 487 [21] S. Jamil, A.R. Alvi, S.R. Khan, M.R.S. Ashraf Janjua, Layered double hydroxides (LDHs):
488 Synthesis and applications. *Prog. Chem.* 31(2019) 394-412.
- 489 [22] Y.Y. Wang, M. Qiao, Y.F. Li, S.Y. Wang, Tuning surface electronic configuration of NiFe
490 LDHs nanosheets by introducing cation vacancies (Fe or Ni) as highly efficient electrocatalysts
491 for oxygen evolution reaction, *Small* 14(2018) 1800136.
- 492 [23] S.X. Chen, Y.F. Huang, X.X. Han, Z.L. Wu, C. Lai, J. Wang, Q. Deng, Z.L. Zeng, S.G. Deng,
493 Corrigendum to "Simultaneous and efficient removal of Cr(VI) and methyl orange on LDHs
494 decorated porous carbons", *Chem. Eng. J.* 359(2019) 1679-1680.
- 495 [24] K.Z. Li, M.J. Liu, S.K. Li, F.Z. Huang, L. Wang, H. Zhang, Design on hierarchical P doped

- 496 Ni(OH)₂@Ni-Co LDH core-shell heterojunction as an advanced battery-like electrode for high
497 performance hybrid supercapacitors. *J. of Alloy. Compd.* 817(2020) 152712.
- 498 [25] G.L. Fan, F. Li, D.G. Evans, X. Duan, Catalytic applications of layered double hydroxides:
499 recent advances and perspectives, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 43(2014) 7040-7066.
- 500 [26] N. Chubar, R. Gilmour, V. Gerda, M. Mičušík, M. Omastova, K. Heister, P. Man, J. Fraissard,
501 V. Zaitsev, Layered double hydroxides as the next generation inorganic anion exchangers:
502 Synthetic methods versus applicability, *Adv. Colloid Interfac.* 245(2017) 62-80.
- 503 [27] S.P. Paredes, M.A. Valenzuela, G. Fetter, S.O. Flores, TiO₂/MgAl layered double hydroxides
504 mechanical mixtures as efficient photocatalysts in phenol degradation, *J. Phys. Chem. Solids*
505 72(2011) 914-919.
- 506 [28] G. Mascolo, M.C. Mascolo, On the synthesis of layered double hydroxides (LDHs) by
507 reconstruction method based on the "memory effect", *Micropor. Mesopor. Mat.* 214(2015)
508 246-248.
- 509 [29] Z.J. Huang, P.X. Wu, Y.H. Lu, X.R. Wang, N.W. Zhu, Z. Dang, Enhancement of photocatalytic
510 degradation of dimethyl phthalate with nano-TiO₂ immobilized onto hydrophobic layered
511 double hydroxides: A mechanism study, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 246-247(2013) 70-78.
- 512 [30] Y.C. Jiang, Y. Song, Y.M. Li, W.C. Tian, Z.C. Pan, P.Y. Yang, Y.S. Li, Q.F. Gu, L.F. Hu,
513 Charge transfer in ultrafine LDH nanosheets/graphene interface with superior capacitive
514 energy storage performance, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 9(2017) 37645-37654.
- 515 [31] Y.M. Liao, J. Yu, S.Q. Wei, Z.M. Jiang, Adsorption effect and mechanism of aqueous arsenic
516 on FeMnNi-LDHs, *Environmental Science* 42(2021) 293-304.

- 517 [32] C.X. Qian, X.N. Yu, T.W. Zheng, Y.Q. Chen, Review on bacteria fixing CO₂ and
518 bio-mineralization to enhance the performance of construction materials, *J. CO₂ Util.* 55(2022)
519 101849.
- 520 [33] X.N. Yu, H. Rong, Seawater based MICP cements two-phase/one-phase cemented sand blocks,
521 *Appl. Ocean Res.* 118(2022) 102972.
- 522 [34] X.N. Yu, H.Q. Yang, H. Wang, A cleaner biocementation method of soil via microbially
523 induced struvite precipitation: A experimental and numerical analysis, *J. Environ. Manage.*
524 316(2022) 115280.
- 525 [35] Z. Tang, W.G. Li, Q. Peng, V.W.Y. Tam, K.J. Wang, Study on the failure mechanism of
526 geopolymetric recycled concrete using digital image correlation method, *J. Sustain.*
527 *Cement-Based Mater.* 11(2022) 113-126.
- 528 [36] A. Singh, Z. Duan, J. Xiao, Q. Liu, Incorporating recycled aggregates in self-compacting
529 concrete: a review, *J. Sustain. Cement-Based Mater.* 9(2020) 165-189.
- 530 [37] J.J. Assaad, Influence of recycled aggregates on dynamic/static stability of self-consolidating
531 concrete, *J. Sustain. Cement-Based Mater.* 6(2017) 345-365
532